

Enhancing Public Transportation Operations through Service Reinforcement, Bunching Detection and Data-Driven Analysis

Andoni Mujika^{1,2}, Iker Arandia¹, Itziar Urbieta¹, Harbil Arregui¹ and Estíbaliz Loyo¹

1 Fundación Vicomtech, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA),
`iurbieta@vicomtech.org`

2 Department of Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence, University of the
Basque Country (UPV/EHU),
`andoni.mujika@ehu.eus`

Abstract. This paper introduces a system designed to assist a public transport operator, in identifying services requiring reinforcement, predicting or detecting service bunching, and refining schedules based on historical data analysis. In routes with low frequency, the system analyzes factors such as occupancy, punctuality, punctuality trend, and the percentage of completed routes to generate a prioritized list of services that could benefit from additional vehicles for reinforcement. For high-frequency routes, the system examines the distances between consecutive vehicles and their behavior to identify groups of services that may result in bunching scenarios. Furthermore, a regression study is conducted to uncover punctuality patterns that may necessitate a reevaluation of official schedules.

Keywords: computational geometry, graph theory, Hamilton cycles

1 Introduction

Public transportation is crucial for modern society due to its efficiency, democracy, and sustainability in reducing congestion and improving air quality. It plays a pivotal role in making cities more livable and eco-friendly. However, reliability is a critical concern for public transportation, especially in high-frequency services. For that, fleet supervisors must manage the allocation of backup resources to ensure adherence to schedules and reduce service bunching, making their decision-making process complex.

Like in other works [1], in this study, we demonstrate how our system assists fleet supervisors in identifying services requiring reinforcement in advance, predicting or detecting service bunching, and refining official schedules based on historical data analysis. The system primarily processes messages (stop passes and GPS position mainly) from the public transportation fleet. Additionally, it incorporates the daily schedule, which outlines the expected times for each service to pass through each stop.

Upon receiving these messages, the system updates its status, enabling the supervisor to monitor real-time information. This includes a list of services that may require reinforcement and situations where the predicted time difference between two or more services is diminishing. Moreover, the system enables analysis beyond real-time monitoring and offers a thorough evaluation of the services' performance. This includes comparing them to historical data from previous days and extracting further valuable insights.

2 Related Work

Extensive research in the field of operations research and transportation science has made noteworthy progress in tackling the issue of bus service reliability. An effective strategy involves implementing headway-based control, a methodology centered around regulating the time intervals between buses to achieve a consistent and balanced service frequency [2]. In the context of bus bunching, the utilization of headway-based solutions enables a precise evaluation of traffic conditions, road congestion, and various factors that have a substantial influence on bus operations and contribute to the phenomenon of bunching [3]. For low-frequency transportation lines where the next service is too distant to resolve the problem, specific reinforcements address punctuality or occupancy issues that arise in particular services [4].

Numerous studies have underscored the significance of timetabling and vehicle scheduling. Gkiotsalitis et al. [5] present an alternative approach that integrates rescheduling and bus holding strategies to improve passenger waiting experience, specifically addressing excessive waiting times (EWT) at bus stops. Wagale et al. [6] employ an optimization approach that incorporates real-time data event parameters, such as bus stop departures, arrivals, and bus traffic costs, to enhance the bus scheduling process.

3 Service Reinforcement

Our system provides the supervisor with a roster of services that necessitate reinforcement. To do this, the system creates a ranking of services to be reinforced ordered by a parameter (called susceptibility to reinforcement) that considers several factors extracted from the data received from each service.

This is the defined formula for susceptibility to reinforcement parameter:

$$S = R(\alpha O + \beta P + \gamma T)$$

where S is the susceptibility to reinforcement, R is the percentage of the route remaining, O is the vehicle occupancy parameter, P is the punctuality of the service, T is the trend of the service in punctuality and α, β, γ are weights of the linear formula. All described parameters go from 0 to 1.

Note that the percentage of the path remaining, R , appears by multiplying the linear combination comprising all the other parameters. If this value is close

to 0 (the service is close to ending), it does not make sense for this service to be reinforced, and therefore this value of R must cancel the entire formula, no matter how high the other parameters are.

3.1 Percentage of route remaining

Depending on the type of communication received from the vehicle, the percentage of the remaining route is calculated in two different ways. If the data received is from one stop to the next, the percentage between the distance traveled to that stop, and the total distance is calculated. On the other hand, if the data is a GPS position, the distance between the previous stop and the point received is calculated. Thus, this distance is added to the total distance to the last stop and then divided by the entire service length.

However, it is different to reinforce a service close to garages (where the reinforcement vehicles rest) or one that will need a long time to be reinforced. If the route is very far, the service may have ended when the reinforcement arrives.

So, in the calculation of R , the percentage of the remaining route, if a service needs reinforcement at some point on the route, we will have to consider that the reinforcement will take time to reach the next stop, and it will have to be done before the service arrives (in theory). Therefore, using the estimated times from depots to each stop, we will take the first stop where the reinforcement comes before the service. Thus, in the general formula, instead of multiplying the percentage of the missed route, we will multiply the percentage of the missed route from the stop where the reinforcement would start. If a reinforcement cannot arrive on time for any stop of the route, it would take 0 value.

3.2 Vehicle occupancy

People getting on and off the vehicle are known at each stop. With these data, the system updates the number of passengers traveling in each vehicle. To convert this number into the parameter O , which goes from 0 to 1, a threshold is defined (different for each type of vehicle), and penalization begins once that value is exceeded. Therefore, the parameter is 0 below the threshold and at the threshold itself and increases proportionally to 1 (maximum capacity of the vehicle).

3.3 Service punctuality

Of the four parameters in the formula, two are related to the punctuality of the vehicle: P and T . This punctuality is calculated simply when the message is a stop pass since we also have the theoretical stop pass. However, when the message received is a GPS position, this information must be converted to a punctuality value. The GPS point is placed in a segment of the shape corresponding to the route that the vehicle is carrying out. Then, the distance between the previous stop and the point and between the point and the next stop are calculated. In this way, we can obtain the percentage made between the stops, and knowing

the theoretical time between these two stops, the time remaining for the vehicle to reach the next stop is proportionally calculated.

Then, the deviation of the route from the theoretical route, p , is first calculated. Then, to have the final parameter P inside the interval $[0, 1]$, we compute $P = 1 - e^{-ap}$ where a is a parameter to modulate the penalization due to the lack of punctuality.

With this formula, we get that when punctuality is good, the difference between the expected time and the real-time is 0, and the value of the parameter P is 0. The value increases with the minutes lost until it approaches 1.

3.4 Service punctuality trend

When it comes to the punctuality of the service, we must consider if the service is getting more and more delayed, it is stuck in a constant delay, or it is recovering part of its delay. Those that are doing worse will be more likely to be reinforced.

Therefore, the moving average of punctuality is calculated with a window of length k . The difference between the last moving averages is the one marked by the T parameter. If this difference exceeds a given threshold, it will begin to penalize, and below it will be 0.

4 Bunching Detection

As previously mentioned, on high-frequency routes, the spacing between services takes precedence over punctuality. The EWT serves as an indicator to comprehend the status of a particular route or the entire fleet concerning this aspect. However, the objective of our system is to pinpoint the specific services that require corrective action with greater precision.

Therefore, we define a parameter PB (predisposition to bunching) that will serve to order services regarding their need for corrective actions:

$$PB = \mu CD + \nu BT$$

where μ and ν are scalar parameters that can be defined by the public transportation operator based on their experience and their needs. CD is the current inter-service distance and BT is the bunching trend.

4.1 Current Inter-service Distance

When identifying a vehicle v_n that has to modify its service, we consider the distance from the previous vehicle, v_{n-1} , and the distance to the subsequent vehicle, v_{n+1} . The objective of the operator is to maintain both distances aligned with the theoretical distance t .

In Figure 1 three different bunching situations are shown. The first one is the ideal one (both distances equal to t). In the second one, even though v_n is too close to the previous services, it seems that it is v_{n-1} the service that has to

be modified because the second distance is correct. In this case, the system will detect the problem when computing PB for v_{n-1} . In the third situation, v_n is the vehicle that is causing the bunching and the one that should be corrected.

Fig. 1. i) no bunching, ii) bunching due to v_{n-1} 's delay, iii) bunching due to v_n 's delay.

Following these principles, we define $CD = |dist(v_{n-1}, v_n) - t| + |dist(v_n, v_{n+1}) - t|$. This way, CD will be 0 in ideal situations and any deviations from neighboring services will increase its value. Additionally, this prioritizes situations such as the third one depicted in Figure 1 over the second one.

4.2 Bunching Trend

Currently, corrective actions for addressing bunching are initiated upon a driver reporting an issue via radio, such as expressing lateness or visually observing the preceding service. The objective of this bunching detection is to proactively anticipate the problem by considering the trend of bunching.

Thus, a moving average of the inter-service distance is employed to penalize services that progressively deviate from the expected distance they should maintain. This is crucial since a small deviation typically deteriorates rapidly.

5 Historical Data Analysis

The points pictured in Figure 2 show the historical behavior of the services on a route. We analyze how the punctuality of the service varies concerning the percentage of the route completed, that is, how punctuality varies in the different areas of the route.

As can be seen, the punctuality of the service is not independent of the percentage of the route. The punctuality of the different services follows a general pattern that can be used to model each route. Thus, a polynomial regression model can give us good results. However, we have to evaluate the goodness-of-fit, since not all the routes have such clear behaviors.

In the Figure, we show the polynomial regression carried out. Once the regression was done, the obtained polynomial was tested with new data (for the same route) and we checked that the behavior extracted from previous data was valid.

Fig. 2. Regression curve for the analysed route

Historical data can help to improve the theoretical value of stop passes since it can detect permanent punctuality patterns. We compare in Figure 3 the theoretical value, the corrected theoretical value, and the real value of the steps made by the services of a given route.

Fig. 3. Theoretical steps (crosses), corrected theoretical steps (squares), and real steps of the services of a route

In this case, in most of the routes, the corrected step is closer to reality than the theoretical one.

6 Conclusions

Within this paper, we have unveiled a support system for fleet supervisors overseeing public transportation operations. The system works as a guide to supervisors concerning low-frequency routes, suggesting potential reinforcement with additional vehicles, as well as high-frequency routes, signaling the need for corrective actions performed by the vehicles themselves. In addition to providing real-time assistance, the system also enables the analysis of historical data to uncover punctuality patterns that could warrant schedule adjustments.

Contrary to expectations, it remains compulsory that the supervisor is responsible for making decisions and communicating corrective actions via radio.

Furthermore, certain corrective actions, including determining the number of stops to skip in order to regulate service distance, are performed by drivers independently, without any supervision.

Therefore, the forthcoming stages in advancing our system will not be related to automating decision-making. We will focus on enhancing the support provided by the system to the supervisor. Regarding the detection of bunching, we believe that occupancy plays a significant role in the gradual delay of a service and the advancement of the subsequent service. Thus, we intend to incorporate occupancy as one of the influencing factors in measuring the predisposition to bunching.

On the other hand, when it comes to historical data analysis, we plan to conduct a more detailed study to identify patterns of punctuality during peak and off-peak hours.

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